

How can the Christian worshipping community be a safe place for those living with non-suicidal self-injury?

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As a practising Christian and having overcome her own trauma-related mental health issues Joanna Naomi Douglas is passionate about trauma-informed theology and building trauma-informed worshipping communities. Joanna is a qualified teacher working with students living with complex social, emotional, educational, and trauma-related mental health needs Joanna. Alongside her teaching role, Joanna is currently pursuing a PhD in trauma-informed theology having previously gained a Masters degree in this field through The University of Manchester (2018). Joanna also holds a BA in Theology from The University of Chester UK (2015).

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Abstract

Within contemporary society, there has been a greater understanding of issues of mental health and well-being. However, it could be argued that this awareness heavily focuses on issues of depression and anxiety and negates research into more complex issues such as non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI). This paper seeks to explore the issue of NSSI and where it fits within Christian theology and the pastoral practices of the Christian worshipping community.

Keywords: self-harm, pastoral, worshipping community, church, self-injury, healing, redemption, non-suicidal

Abbreviations: NSSI – non-suicidal self-injury

Introduction

Today the reality is that “diagnoses for many mental illnesses and disorders are on the rise.”¹ With our postmodern Western society becoming increasingly aware of issues surrounding the causes, effects, and treatments of mental health disorders. Especially as “public visibility of mental health is growing. It is no longer staggering ... to see public figures—politicians, athletes, musicians, actors, and ... [even] the royal family, open up about their personal experiences of mental health.”² This has arguably contributed to the positive way in which the mental wellbeing of people within society is becoming an ever-growing discussion, which is actively being encouraged by various charities and organisations who work to support those living with mental health disorders.³ This research paper seeks to enter that discussion by exploring the role of faith, theology and the Christian worshipping community in the mental well-being of those within its congregations. Despite Christians having a history of increasing involvement in areas of social action their communities have not always been considered a place of safety and acceptance for those who live with mental health issues, including those who self-injure. This paper explores why this may be and how Christian worshipping communities might be able to approach issues of mental well-being and self-injury. This paper has a specific focus on issues of non-suicidal self-injury (NSSI) and seeks to explore how those within the worshipping community could best support others within their communities in a way which would be a safe, accepting, and appropriately supportive place for those who deliberately injure themselves in this way.

Understanding non-suicidal self-injury.

To be able to do this research it is first important to understand what non-suicidal self-injury is and to understand its causes. NSSI is referred to by several different names

such as self-mutilation or self-harm, and is defined as “the deliberate, self-inflicted destruction of the body tissue without suicidal intent and for purposes not socially sanctioned.”⁴ This kind of deliberate self-injury is not a new phenomenon and is not unique to any specific demographic of person. Yet historically, at least in the West, this kind of self-injury has largely been seen as an adolescent female issue. However, with increasing research, we see that this thinking is beginning to be questioned.⁵ Research shows that while the average age for the onset of self-injury is as young as 11 or 12 years old many continue self-injury behaviours long into adulthood, and while there are more females than males who self-injure, currently “the rate of males engaged in self-injury is climbing more rapidly than for females.”⁶

The number one method of self-injury is cutting, where a person engages in the action of physically and deliberately cutting themselves with any number of sharp implements, often repeatedly. However self-injury can also include actions such as pulling hair out, “scratching, burning, hitting, scrubbing, picking or abrading the skin; punching or head-butting the wall; drinking bleach; picking at wounds and warts; refusing medication ... and sewing pieces of material to the skin.”⁷ More serious forms of self-injury can include “self-administered body piercing and ‘tattooing’; and swallowing a range of objects including mobile-phone batteries and zip fasteners.”⁸

The reasons and causes of why people self-injure are complex and far-reaching, it should be noted that although self-injury is statistically associated with suicide, most self-injury is not an attempted suicide and for many it is in fact a means of avoiding it.⁹ However, it has been argued that “everyone engaging in self-harmful behaviours falls along a continuum of suicidal intent.”¹⁰ This continuum of suicidal intent occurs because it is not always easy to distinctly distinguish between suicidal and non-suicidal self-injury as “suicidal intent is complex and can be ambiguous and transient,”¹¹ a healthcare professional’s “judgment about suicidal intent may be different from that stated”¹² by the individual who has injured themselves. Therefore, although self-injuring behaviours are often without suicidal intent, there is still a strong risk factor for suicide found within self-injury, meaning there is a genuine concern for the well-being and life of those who do self-injure. Having said this, it is possible to understand the majority of self-injury as non-suicidal and even as an attempt to protect oneself from choosing to end their own life as “self-harm affords people a means of coping.”¹³ Meaning many individuals who engage in self-injury could also be seeking or desiring healing from the inner pain or mental distress which has led them to these behaviours.

Actions of self-injury have a proven strong link with a wide variety of mental and psychiatric disorders and is found in the diagnostic criteria for several psychiatric disorders such as depression, anxiety, personality disorders and a wide spectrum of trauma-related disorders.¹⁴ However, some argue that NSSI should be understood as a separate syndrome or disorder as opposed to a symptom of other mental health disorders.¹⁵ Either way, what is agreed and widely accepted is that self-injury is related to deep emotional pain and is understood as a way of coping with that pain. Self-injury behaviours have been noted to begin because the person is unable to control or express the pain they feel emotionally within and so as Nancy Alcorn has described self-harm is “the outward expression of pain and hurt deep within.”¹⁶ Self-injury behaviours have

therefore become the way the individual has attempted to express and alleviate their uncontrollable inner pain. NSSI then becomes a coping mechanism for the individual to be able to cope with that inner pain by becoming “a means of escape from reality, ... [and is] adopted [as] a self-destructive coping mechanism for dealing with life.”¹⁷ Although self-injury may provide initial relief from their inner pain or afford them a way of coping it is not long before the destruction of their self-injury behaviours is felt. It is the instant initial relief of emotional and inner pain experienced through the action of self-injury that means the self-injury behaviours become addictive ways of coping, especially as the person has to continue the self-injury behaviours to continue to experience that initial relief.¹⁸

The Church’s position in the mental well-being of its members.

For many Christians who live with NSSI and its addictive and yet destructive behaviours the worshipping community is often one of the first places they turn to for support. For many who live with NSSI the Christian community can be a supportive, safe, and welcoming environment. However, for others, this is not always the case. Self-injury has often been misunderstood and still has a stigma attached to it within wider society and by the worshipping community. As previously mentioned NSSI is often seen as an adolescent female issue and is often attributed to attention-seeking behaviours, which have negative connotations attached to it.¹⁹ However, the roots and reasons for NSSI are far more complex than this. While it is necessary to recognise that it is possible that for some their self-injury behaviours might indeed be due to seeking attention, or a cry for support, it should not be ignored that the individual is seeking this attention by mutilating their own body and even putting their very lives at risk. The fact that they feel the need to mutilate themselves in this way to gain the attention they crave is a desperate reality and one that I argue the Christian worshipping community must respond well to.

Over the past few decades, there have been many groups and charities, both Christian and secular, forming and growing with a particular focus on mental health issues. However, it has been noted that within many of these faith-based support groups, programs, and social action projects “a lot of the activity is focused at a ‘softer’ end of the spectrum”²⁰ when dealing with mental health issues. Much of the growing discussions about mental health cover a wide emphasis on issues of depression and anxiety, however, it is rarer to see the discussion on mental health move further past these issues into a discussion on more complex mental disorders. It is often these same faith-based and social action groups, as well as many secular organisations and charities, who are the ones to provide the main training, support and resources from which worshipping communities and their leaders gain most of their understanding of mental health issues and even how to support those within their communities who struggle with issues of mental health. Therefore, it could be argued that it is the case that Christian worshipping communities often gain a greater understanding on issues of depression and anxiety rather than issues related to more complex mental health disorders. This perhaps has led to the Christian community not being best informed or equipped to support those living with complex mental health issues such as NSSI. While this is not a major concern, there are arguably concerns which should be raised, as those within Christian worshipping communities are not exempt from the human reality of complex mental health issues. Therefore, when those struggling with NSSI do turn to these faith-based organisations and Christian worshipping communities for

support, it is evidenced that this can cause problems and even further damage to the individual seeking support.²¹

Carol L. Schnabl Schweitzer explains that these problems arise because those with complex mental health issues “frequently create crises in the context of congregational life”²² which untrained or unequipped church workers are not prepared for. Schweitzer’s research focuses more specifically on those who live with borderline personality disorder (BPD). However, NSSI is strongly linked to BPD and Schweitzer recognises NSSI behaviours as one of the causes of these crises in churches. Schweitzer describes how individuals who struggle with complex mental health issues, such as BPD and NSSI, often present to church leaders and pastoral workers with crisis issues such as violence, anger, manipulation, and retaliation aimed at those offering supportive care. Schweitzer notes that this expression of anger and manipulation is “especially the case when ministers and church members attempt to set healthy boundaries with these individuals whose fears of abandonment are triggered when a healthy boundary feels like a failure of empathy.”²³ This can, at times, create a great number of challenges within worshipping communities as those who live with NSSI therefore may require a greater level of compassion, tolerance and understanding towards their complex behaviours than those who do not live with NSSI. Further training for church leaders and supportive members and a deeper understanding of the way NSSI effects the person, mentally as well as the physical effects which their self-injury causes is therefore important. Schweitzer argues that this training should not just be a onetime training as there is a “real and continued need for more knowledge and resources for those [in the worshipping community] who are responsible for the pastoral care of their members.”²⁴

Theological approaches to mental well-being.

Many people, including some Christians, argue that theology or religion has no place within the discussion about mental health as it should be a discussion for solely the sciences. Fraser Watts believes that this is because historically the church has framed mental health within the concept of sin, and even “in terms of whether people are ‘mad’ or bad’.”²⁵ Arguably, even the way that the Gospel narrative of the Geresene demoniac is commonly used by Christians to illustrate self-cutting within the Bible may present a negative or demonic connotation to NSSI.²⁶ Watts says that “It may seem bland and uncontroversial to suggest that theology and science are compatible and complementary. However, on the specific topic of mental health it seems surprisingly controversial, and may be a minority position.”²⁷ That said, this does not have to be the case, sciences such as psychology and psychiatry can be viewed “as compatible with a religious perspective, ... [as] together they provide complementary perspectives that enrich our overall understanding.”²⁸ As NSSI is a recognised as a diagnosable disorder, one that Christianity and the church cannot be removed from, it is therefore a part of the human condition that “calls for theological reflection.”²⁹

Watts compares the secular approach to mental health disorders, which he notes is to want to get rid of them and their symptoms, to that of the “religious perspective, [which] is more likely to ask how there can be a path through mental health problems to something better than what prevailed before.”³⁰ This need to return to what was before the pain is arguable because Christian theology is built upon the redemptive, transformative and saving act of Christ’s death and resurrection. This resurrection theology of redemption is “rooted in the concept of repairing or restoring what is damaged, [where] something or someone is freed from a situation of harm and changed for the better.”³¹ One theological approach to relating this redemptive discourse to

issues of NSSI is a theology of repairing, restoring, and transforming, where for many who live with NSSI it is a position of hope for something better despite living with self-injury behaviours. It is the hope of one day stop self-injury following redemptive healing. This could allow space for a Christian who lives with NSSI to ask how their self-destructive and self-injury behaviours could become a source of blessing to them through Jesus. NSSI becomes something to overcome and heal from and hope is found in the promise of Jesus to make all things new. Yet, for some Christian, the concept of something so damaging and destructive as self-injury being a source of hope is an unpalatable concept. However, it could be argued that to look for hope within NSSI is not to deny or to attempt to justify the distress, pain and destruction that NSSI causes, “rather it is to adopt a frame of reference broad enough to be able to recognise *both* the distress *and* the opportunities that mental health problems bring.”³²

Nancy Alcorn argues that this restorative healing approach is a theological perspective of healing, freedom and overcoming which is rooted in the redemptive discourse, where Jesus has overcome all pain, hardship and brokenness through His resurrection. She argues this by recognising that a desire to escape the reality of emotional pain “is one of the main causes of self-harm.”³³ She describes how painful memories and trauma experiences “may lie dormant for a while, but they will always resurface, often at the worst possible time,”³⁴ and debilitate the person who lives with them, describing NSSI as a way in which an individual has been debilitated by their pain and trauma.³⁵ Alcorn argues that by verbalising the reality of this pain to another who the individual trusts they would no longer need to escape their painful reality through self-injury as they would be able to find healing, and what she calls “freedom”³⁶ from the pain they carry. She argues that by finding this healing and freedom the individual would therefore in turn be healed and free from NSSI, by which she means able to stop all addictive self-injury behaviours, describing this as to “break the hold self-harm has over their life.”³⁷ She presents that this is possible because “with God’s help ... [all things can be] overcome.”³⁸ This theological view of healing could be presented by many Christian worshipping communities and Christian groups as the answer to most issues of mental health including those of NSSI.

Theological concepts of redemptive healing and overcoming are indeed rooted theologically and Biblically within the Passion narrative and are rightly associated with the healing rhetoric. However, I argue that presenting them in this way to those who suffer from mental health disorders and issues such as NSSI may be problematic. Alcorn presents her argument by suggesting that an individual can break free from all self-injuring behaviours by simply talking about that which caused the deep-rooted inner pain with a trusted other and that by believing in and trusting in God and His ability to overcome all things. Arguably, this presentation of healing of NSSI is far too simplistic and so it is perhaps even dangerous to present it in this way to those who live with NSSI. It must be recognised that NSSI is a deeply complex disorder, and is a highly addictive coping behaviour where the person may not yet have any other way to express or appropriately cope or deal with their painful feelings or memories and so to suggest the individual must, at least try to, stop their self-injury behaviours without offering anything in its place to cope with and express the pain is dangerous as self-injury can be a means to avoid suicide. The church and theology must understand that inner pain, such as that which lies at the root of NSSI, is rarely if ever, healed by simply looking to the redemption promised in the resurrection of Christ. Therefore, presenting healing in the way such as Alcorn does becomes dangerous to those who live with NSSI as it makes promises of a simplistic healing that in reality may not come so easily. If theology and the Christian worshipping community make promises of healing for the

individual living with NSSI in a seemingly simplistic discourse and this healing does not come so easily, the individual may be left only with the age-old theological question of where is God in the face of suffering? To be left with this question when healing has been promised and not yet come can be distressing, not only to the person seeking healing but also to those supporting them. The question of where God is in suffering is a unique and theological injury because to question where God is in times of suffering is to experience a felt absence of God.³⁹ This paper argues that the pastoral response needed to be offered to those who live with NSSI is to experience God, His love and His compassion within their pain and vulnerabilities rather than to present simplistic healing where he is distant and aloof waiting for the individual to come to Him. It is through God coming and meeting the individual in their pain that an individual might find the tools they need to overcome or restore from their pain because when someone has lived in the last place, in the place of pain, and then discovers that Jesus is with them in this place as well, it is truly good news.

The Church Becoming a Safe Place for those who live with None Suicidal Self Injury.

In his book *The Dangerous Act of Loving Your Neighbor: Seeing Others Through the Eyes of Jesus*, Mark Labberton talks about those who are broken and hurting needing love and compassion. He argues that “in a complicated world of profound injustice, the crisis of the human heart is crucial to social transformation.”⁴⁰ Presenting that “changing our world depends on changing our hearts; how we perceive, name and act in the world.”⁴¹ He recognises that many Christians see the social injustices of the world and wish to transform them. For many of who live in a level of peace and wholeness afforded to them, either by privilege, money, good upbringing or through the experience of the transformative love of God in their life they cannot in good conscience not respond to the social injustice and brokenness they see in the world around them. If the redemption offered by Jesus through the Passion narrative can indeed offer the ability to restore what is damaged and bring about transformation in the lives of those who are hurting, such as those who live with NSSI then I argue that the Passion must be presented to those who are hurting and who live with NSSI in a way that does not leave the individual questioning where was God in the suffering. Arguably, the church must turn its heart to the transformation of the world through Jesus. We read in Matthew 22:36-40 that Jesus told His followers to “love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind. [He called this] ... the first and greatest commandment.” He then went on to say that “the second is like it: ‘Love your neighbour as yourself.’” Jesus is clear in His commandment to His followers, to love God and to love one another. If Christians are to truly live this commandment out, they are called to love. This love is not just love those who are like them or are within their worshipping communities, but for all people in society. Therefore, arguably love is the place to begin this transformative ministry towards those who are hurting, such as those live with NSSI.

Many church leaders and pastoral workers have come to understand that the demands of working with someone who suffers from complex mental health issues such as NSSI “are emotionally draining and at times divisive in the congregation.”⁴² It is often the case that individuals who live with NSSI “have the capacity to drain a minister and a congregation of their emotional, spiritual, and even financial resources.”⁴³ Schweizer argues that loving an individual who lives with NSSI would mean expressing a deeper level of understanding, compassion and tolerance despite the way that working with the individual is draining. She argues there are several practical things ministers

and pastoral workers within churches should put in place to be able to better provide compassionate and loving support to those who struggle with mental health issues such as NSSI. She argues that first and foremost there should be good, clear, and defined boundaries, which include the need for those loving the individual to be able to at times say 'no'. She argues that "having a healthy respect for our own sense of self is what enables ministers to have the courage to both work with and tolerate the onslaught that often accompanies helping someone who suffers."⁴⁴ Individuals who live with NSSI, and other complex mental and trauma-related disorders caused by deep inner pain, "may seem very social but will self-disclose inappropriately. As a result, this person lacks the capacity to engage with others on a deeper level. Moreover, this person will also reject someone with whom he or she has just shared inappropriately."⁴⁵ This is evidenced to have caused a crisis within Christian worshipping communities and is often challenging for ministers, leaders and church members alike to deal with. For any community to be a safe environment for all, especially those who cannot regulate what of their pain they disclose with others or stop the addictive self-injuring coping mechanisms clear and structured boundaries are needed and will provide the foundations for good loving and supportive relationships for all within the congregation. It is from the foundation of these boundaries that good and healthy relationships of love maybe formed within the worshipping community.

To love the other is to accept the other within and despite their pain and brokenness, not just loving the other if they are able to find healing from that pain. For those who live with NSSI there is a deep pain and perhaps may be experiences of abandonment and rejection. Therefore, Labberton argues that to bring healing to the broken is to truly love the individual as Jesus loves them and is not to attempt to fix them or to bring about healing. He argues that expecting individuals to change and heal in a way that is impossible for them in their current lived experience is not to truly love them like Jesus does.⁴⁶ Therefore, to truly love our neighbour who lives with deep inner emotional pain and who self-injures as a way of coping with this pain means that the Christian worshipping community should not tell them that transformation and healing is needed. The church is not a safe place for all when such transformation is presented as a simple answer and does not allow the individual to experience love in who they are in their broken and painful reality of NSSI. To love our neighbour is to know them and to offer a space of belonging and acceptance, despite their pain and vulnerabilities. There is nothing more loving than to look at somebody who is hurting and tell them that you are with them, that you accept them no matter what they do, and most importantly that despite their pain, despite their self-destructive behaviours, the community loves them, accepts them and welcomes them just as Jesus does.⁴⁷

Conclusion.

This paper has explored how a Christian worshipping community might best become a supportive and safe environment for those living with non-suicidal self-injury. We have come to understand how NSSI is an addictive coping mechanism which can afford an individual a way of avoiding suicide despite its destructiveness. While this paper does not justify actions of NSSI it does recognise that the Christian worshipping community presenting concepts of simplistic redemptive healing could be damaging for those living with NSSI because what happens if healing does not occur? This paper contends that to be a safe and supportive environment for Christians living with NSSI the church must show tolerance, understanding and the love of Jesus to those living with NSSI by accepting them despite the NSSI behaviours and allowing them to meet Jesus in their

pain even if that means that they continue their NSSI behaviours for a time, because it is in pain and vulnerability that hope can be found rather than despite it.

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- ¹⁹ Stanford, Sarah, Jones Michael P and Hudson, Jennifer, L. “Appreciating Complexity in Adolescent Self-Harm Risk Factors”
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- ²⁴ *ibid*
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- ²⁶ Olsen, Ann Elizabeth. *The Cry Among Us*.
- ²⁷ This and the preceding three quotations are from Watts, “Theology and Science of Mental Health and Well-being,” 338.
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³³ This and the preceding five quotations are from Alcorn Nancy. *Mercy For Self Harm*.

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³⁵ *ibid*

³⁶ *ibid*

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⁴⁰ This and the preceding five quotations are from Labberton, Mark. *The Dangerous Act of Loving Your Neighbor: Seeing Others Through the Eyes of Jesus*.

⁴¹ *ibid*

⁴² This and the preceding three quotations are from Alcorn Schweitzer, Carol L. Schnabl “Resilience Revisited: What Ministers Need to Know About Borderline Personality Disorder,”

⁴³ *ibid*

⁴⁴ *ibid*

⁴⁵ *ibid*

⁴⁶ This and the preceding quotation are from Labberton, Mark. *The Dangerous Act of Loving Your Neighbor: Seeing Others Through the Eyes of Jesus*.

⁴⁷ *ibid*